

**METHODOLOGY FOR THE FORMATION OF THE INTEGRATION OF SPEECH
AND THINKING BY TEACHING STUDENTS TO WRITE ESSAYS**

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Abstract. This article discusses the methodology of forming the integration of speech and thinking among students by teaching them how to write an essay. The main approaches to the integration of speech and thinking in the educational process are analyzed. The experience of using essay writing tasks as a means of developing students' critical thinking and academic writing skills is considered. The effectiveness of this technique for improving the quality of specialist training is substantiated.

Keywords: integration of speech and thinking, essay writing training, critical thinking, academic writing.

INTRODUCTION

The integration of speech and thinking is an important component of professional training of students in modern schools [1]. Effective speech activity is inextricably linked with the development of thinking, and the ability to competently present ideas in writing is very important for the further success of students [2]. A number of studies confirm the need for purposeful work on the integration of speech and thinking in the educational process using active learning methods [3].

One effective means of implementing this approach is to include essay writing tasks in the learning process. Various aspects of using this genre of academic writing to develop certain skills among students are considered in the works of both foreign and domestic teachers [4]. At the same time, a sufficient amount of research is devoted to the methodology of teaching students to write essays as a means of combining speech and thinking.

The purpose of this article is to analyze the features of the methodology of forming the integration of speech and thinking in students by including tasks related to writing an essay in the educational process.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

During the research, an analysis of local and foreign literature on the issues of integration of education and speech in the school education system was carried out, the experience of using written assignments of various genres was studied for the development of such skills in students. Emphasis was placed on research on the use of the essay as an educational tool, as well as on methodological aspects of teaching students to write essays.

The following methods were used in the research process: analysis of scientific and methodological literature, generalization of pedagogical experience, modeling of the educational process.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The analysis of the literature showed that currently, various methods aimed at unifying speech and thinking among students are widely used in the world education practice [5]. One of the most effective approaches has been recognized as using active and interactive forms of

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learning, particularly written assignments that require detailed responses and the application of critical thinking skills.

For this purpose, tasks related to essay writing are being actively introduced into the curricula of foreign schools [6]. Their performance involves not only presenting certain information, but also analyzing the facts and expressing your point of view on a particular problem based on evidence. This approach makes it possible to form students' thinking culture and written speech culture at the same time.

The results of a number of experimental studies show the effectiveness of using an essay to develop critical thinking skills, the ability to logically and reasonably form ideas, and research skills in students [7]. It is noted that the constant practice of writing essays during schooling allows to develop the ability to analyze information and problems in depth, to see different aspects of the same issue.

Summarizing the experience of using the essay in the local education system, it also shows the effectiveness of this genre of academic writing to integrate speech and thinking among students [8]. At the same time, the methodological aspects of teaching essay writing have not been sufficiently disclosed.

Based on the analysis of literature and the generalization of pedagogical experience, a methodology was developed for the integration of speech and thinking among students by introducing systematic tasks on writing essays into the educational process. This method includes the following main components:

- Introducing students to the features and principles of essay writing. Analysis of samples.
- The teacher will give problem questions and assignments that require writing an essay.
- Advice and help to students in the planning and writing stage of the essay.
- Analysis and evaluation of the essay by the teacher. Formulate recommendations for improving essay writing skills.
- Provide advice on eliminating defects, correcting errors.
- Making essay writing assignments more complicated on a regular basis.

The implementation of this methodology within the framework of specific subjects allows students to regularly use analytical and logical operations, to form their position when considering various issues and problems and to stimulate the reasoning skills, which helps the integration of speech and thinking of students.

DISCUSSION

In order to test the proposed methodology, an experimental study was conducted based on the 10th school in Nukus. 54 students of the 8th-9th grade, divided into experimental and control groups, took part in the research.

During one quarter, targeted works on teaching essay writing were conducted with the students of the experimental group as part of practical training in relevant subjects. Implementation of the methodology included all the components described above. Students of the control group wrote essays within the framework of the standard program without using special methodological methods.

The following parameters were evaluated in both groups by testing and analyzing the written work at the beginning and end of the experiment:

- knowledge of logical operations (analysis, generalization, data classification, etc.);
- the ability to justify one's point of view when considering a problem;
- knowledge of the structure and linguistic tools used in the essay genre.

Comparison of the results of the control and experimental groups at the beginning of the experiment did not reveal significant differences in all analyzed parameters. After the implementation of the formative program, the results of the experimental group were much higher. Thus, the percentage of highly logical and reasoning students increased from 26% to 52%, and the average - from 42% to 48%. A similar dynamic can be observed in relation to the structural and linguistic design of texts. In the control group, the increase in these parameters was insignificant.

Thus, the results of the experimental work confirm the effectiveness of the developed methodology of using essay writing tasks to combine speech and thinking in students.

CONCLUSION

The analysis shows the effectiveness of using essay writing tasks in the educational process of the university as a means of integrated formation of students' speech and thinking. This approach allows students to develop critical thinking skills, research skills, and communication skills.

The developed methodology of teaching students to write an essay can be useful for teachers to improve the quality of professional training of future specialists. Further research can be directed to study the effectiveness of the proposed methodology in relation to specific educational areas and subjects.

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